

The Neutron Kinetics Code FENNECS for the Safety Assessment of MMRs, SMRs and Innovative Reactor Concepts

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ABSTRACT

FENNECS is a few-group neutron kinetics code based on the finite element method. Through its geometric flexibility, it is not limited to reactor cores featuring regular cartesian or hexagonal lattice arrangements but can also handle the more complex geometries of Small Modular Reactors (SMR) and in particular Micro Modular Reactors (MMRs) with rotating control drums and other innovative concepts including Generation IV designs. Starting with the implementation of a steady state diffusion solver, successfully applied to the simulation of a Sodium-cooled Fast Reactor within the EU project ESNII and a prismatic High-Temperature Gas-cooled Reactor within an OECD benchmark, FENNECS has been continuously extended by numerous features. Among these are a transient simulation capability, coupling with the GRS system code ATHLET and the subchannel code CTF, implementation of the simplified SP_3 transport method for state steady and transient simulations, discontinuous Galerkin approach with Assembly Discontinuity Factors (ADFs), capability to simulate rotating control drums in addition to conventional control rods, simulation of neutron poisoning and decay heat. With AC² 2023, FENNECS became a module of this GRS reactor simulation code package. This paper presents an overview of FENNECS and its various ranges of application.

Keywords: FENNECS, Finite Element Method, MMR, SMR, Generation-IV

1. INTRODUCTION

The deterministic approach and the stochastic concept behind the Monte Carlo method represent the two fundamental branches to treat reactor physics by solving the Boltzmann transport equation and its approximations, e.g., the diffusion or simplified transport methods. While the deterministic approach is computationally by far more efficient, in particular for time dependent problems, it has to cope with discretization errors and – except for, e.g., the method of characteristics – requires the preparation of problem-dependent macroscopic cross sections. The Monte Carlo method, on the other hand, applies problem-independent continuous-energy nuclear basis data. There is also no need to discretize the geometry and theoretically no limitation in the geometry description. The stochastic approach, however, suffers from statistical uncertainties and huge computational demands which makes the Monte Carlo method impracticable for time-dependent problems. Therefore, a deterministic approach combined with sufficient geometric flexibility could be a good compromise for the safety assessment of not only Generation IV reactor concepts, but also for MMRs and SMRs. The Finite ElemeNt NEutroniCS code FENNECS is an attempt to implement such a compromise due to the underlying Finite Element Method (FEM) that provides the required geometric flexibility. This paper gives an overview of FENNECS and its various ranges of application, starting with a summary of the major features of FENNECS in the following section. Section 3 presents two application cases which benefit from the geometric flexibility of FENNECS. Section 4 shortly summarizes and concludes the paper.

2. MAJOR CAPABILITIES OF THE FINITE ELEMENT NEUTRONICS CODE FENNECS

FENNECS solves the steady state as well as the transient diffusion as well as the Simplified P_3 (SP_3) transport equations in the continuous Galerkin weighted residual finite element approach, which is

responsible for the high geometric flexibility of the code. Additionally, for the diffusion solver, also the discontinuous variant of the Galerkin formalism is implemented in FENNECS, with the advantage that the latter allows for the possibility to use discontinuity factors. The steady state FENNECS SP₃ solver, presented in [1], was recently extended by a transient one. This new transient solver allows to perform transient calculations with a better accuracy than a diffusion code, but still with acceptable computational demand, hence well below the long calculation times requested by a Monte Carlo code.

In FENNECS, the space discretization is performed with triangular prisms with linear basis functions as spatial elements. Fully implicit time discretization is used for solving the transient diffusion equation. Thermal hydraulic feedback is accounted for by a coupling with two different thermal-hydraulic codes, the thermal-hydraulic system code ATHLET – being a module of the GRS AC² code package – and the thermal-hydraulic subchannel code CTF. For the spatial meshing of the problem geometry, the accompanied Python External Meshing Tool with Yaml input (PEMTY) is applied. Beyond regular cartesian and hexagonal lattices, PEMTY allows the meshing of, e.g., control drums peculiar for micro reactors.

2.1. Rotating Control Drums and Control Rod De-Cusping

Rotating control drums are one of the characteristics that distinguish some Micro Modular Reactors from conventional, e.g., LWR designs. Instead of moving control rods up and down, control drums exhibit a circular shape and are rotated in-plane. The Heat Pipe Micro Reactor (HPMR) [2] is an example of this concept which is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Core layout of the Heat Pipe Micro Reactor detailing a rotating control drum [2].

For simulating the rotation of the control drums, in particular during a transient, FENNECS has been extended to provide this capability. Because the geometry meshing is fixed, it may happen during rotation that material boundaries between the absorber section and the surrounding reflector material moves through a finite element making this element a partially rodded one. First tests revealed that a simple flux-volume weighting results in the well-known control rod cusping effect showing unphysical oscillations of the multiplication factor (for steady state) or of the core power evolution (for transients). The cusping effect originates from homogenization errors of the material mixture of the partially rodded element. While most attempts to treat the cusping effect rely on techniques to compensate or correct this error, a few years ago a different approach proposed a projection-based de-cusping method that defines an effective homogenized cross section for the partially rodded finite element [3]. Unlike the flux-volume weighting method, this method does not involve any approximations. Instead, it exactly solves the weak form of the neutron diffusion equation. This projection-based method has been implemented in FENNECS [4]. As a first application, the control drum reactivity worth of the HPMR has been evaluated with this projection-based technique and compared to the simple flux-volume weighting method. Figure 2 shows that the projection-based method significantly smooths the pronounced cusping effect arising from the standard weighting procedure.

Figure 2. Control drum worth curves of the HPMR obtained with the flux-volume weighting (blue) and projection-based method (orange) of FENNECS [4].

In FENNECS, the projection-based method has been also made available for standard control rods.

2.2. Coupling of FENNECS with the System Code ATHLET and the Subchannel Code CTF

To account for thermal-hydraulic feedback, FENNECS is coupled with the GRS thermal-hydraulic system code ATHLET which is a module of the AC² code package [5]. The internal coupling approach [6] is applied, i.e., the system code models the entire thermal fluid-dynamics and heat transfer of the primary circuit including the core region using the power distribution from FENNECS which treats the 3-d neutron kinetics and provides ATHLET with the power distribution. The exchange of spatial distribution between finite elements and ATHLET data structures is provided through direct memory access and is controlled by a flexible feedback mapping which is automatically generated by FENNECS. In steady-state mode, a few iterations between FENNECS and ATHLET are carried out until convergence. In the current implementation, the time step size for coupled transient simulations is controlled by ATHLET, the time step size used to integrate the fluid-dynamic equations system is also applied in FENNECS. For high-fidelity multiphysics coupled simulations, FENNECS has recently been coupled to the thermal hydraulic subchannel code CTF [7]; details on this coupling will be published in the future.

2.3. Diffusion Approximation and Simplified P₃ Transport Method

FENNECS provides two different approaches to solve the steady state and the time-dependent neutron kinetic equation. The first one is the diffusion approach with its major advantage to be computationally efficient. The second one is the well-known SP₃ transport approach which solves the coupled system of the following two equations:

$$\frac{1}{v} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} F_0(\vec{r}, t) - \frac{2}{v} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} F_1(\vec{r}, t) - \vec{\nabla} \cdot (D_1 \vec{\nabla} F_0(\vec{r}, t)) + \sigma_r F_0(\vec{r}, t) - 2\sigma_r F_1(\vec{r}, t) = s_0(\vec{r}, t) \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{3}{v} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} F_1(\vec{r}, t) - \frac{2}{3v} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} F_0(\vec{r}, t) - \vec{\nabla} \cdot (D_3 \vec{\nabla} F_1(\vec{r}, t)) - \frac{2}{3} \sigma_r F_0(\vec{r}, t) + \frac{4}{3} \sigma_r F_1(\vec{r}, t) + \frac{5}{3} \sigma_t F_1(\vec{r}, t) \\ = -\frac{2}{3} s_0(\vec{r}, t) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Where the energy group index is suppressed and the source term $s_0(\vec{r}, t)$ contains fission, scattering and time-dependent sources. In (1) and (2), the following definitions are used:

$$\begin{aligned} F_{0,g}(\vec{r}, t) &= \phi_{0,g}(\vec{r}, t) + 2\phi_{2,g}(\vec{r}, t) \\ F_{1,g}(\vec{r}, t) &= \phi_{2,g}(\vec{r}, t) \end{aligned}$$

Each of the Eqs. (1) and (2) has the structure of a time-dependent diffusion equation for which FENNECS already provides the solution framework, consisting of the nested loops of inner iteration for solving the within-group steady-state SP_3 equations (1) and (2) and outer iteration, solving either the eigenvalue problem (steady state) or the fixed source problem of a single time step resulting from the fully implicit time integration. The solution of the time-dependent diffusion and SP_3 equations also accounts for the delayed neutron precursor dynamics. More details on the implementation of the steady-state SP_3 equations in FENNECS, in particular on the formulation based on the finite element Galerkin approach, can be found in [1]. Further details about the time-dependent SP_3 implementation in FENNECS, together with verification calculation results, will be published in the near future.

2.4. Further Recent Extensions of FENNECS

2.4.1. Decay power calculation

In order to limit the computational effort, the decay power calculation in FENNECS adopts the approach that is implemented in PARCS [8]. The total power density at location \vec{r} at time t is composed of fission power and decay power as follows:

$$P(\vec{r}, t) = (1 - \alpha) \sum_g \kappa \sigma_g^f(\vec{r}) \phi_g(\vec{r}, t) + \sum_{n=1}^N \zeta_n D_n(\vec{r}, t) \quad (1)$$

$\alpha = \sum_{n=1}^N \alpha_n$ is the power fraction that appears as decay power, $D_n(\vec{r}, t)$ is the spatial concentration of the decay heat precursor group n and ζ_n is the decay constant of the precursor group n . The temporal evolution of the spatial concentration of the decay heat precursor group n is described by the balance of production and decay of the decay heat precursors of that group:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} D_n(\vec{r}, t) = \alpha_n \sum_g \kappa \sigma_g^f(\vec{r}) \phi_g(\vec{r}, t) - \zeta_n D_n(\vec{r}, t) \quad (2)$$

FENNECS solves this equation numerically using a fully implicit time discretization.

2.4.2. Critical boron concentration search and neutron poison calculation

In FENNECS, a linear interpolation scheme is implemented to search for the critical boron concentration [9]. Based on two initial steady-state calculation, one for a subcritical ($c_{subcrit}$ with corresponding eigenvalue $k_{subcrit}$), the other for a supercritical state ($c_{supcrit}$ with corresponding eigenvalue $k_{supcrit}$), a first estimate of the critical boron concentration is calculated by

$$c_{crit} = c_{subcrit} + (c_{supcrit} - c_{subcrit}) \frac{1 - k_{subcrit}}{k_{supcrit} - k_{subcrit}} \quad (3)$$

Depending on either $c_{crit} < 1$ or $c_{crit} > 1$, c_{crit} replaces either $c_{subcrit}$ or $c_{supcrit}$. This procedure is repeated until $k_{eff} = 1 \pm 1$ pcm is obtained.

For the simulation of operational transients, such as load-follow operation, FENNECS can treat the Iodine-Xenon and Promethium-Samarium dynamics. The implementation follows standard textbooks (e.g. [10]) where fully implicit time discretization is applied.

3. Selected Applications

FENNECS has been applied to several reactor concepts ranging from Generation IV designs, e.g., sodium-cooled fast reactor (SFR) [11], lead-cooled fast reactor (LFR) or high-temperature gas-cooled thermal reactor (HTGR) of prismatic type [12], through MMRs [13] up to Light Water-cooled Reactors (LWRs of PWR and BWR type including VVER type [14]). A first validation was done by simulating

neutronic start-up tests of the China Experimental Fast Reactor (CEFR) . This chapter presents two different application cases of FENNECS which benefit from its geometric flexibility. The first one is the simulation of an MMR and the second one is a coupled SFR minicore simulation at pin-by-pin and subchannel level.

3.1. Modeling of an MMR at the Example of the Heat Pipe Micro Reactor

The HPMR [2] already mentioned in section 2.3 has been modelled with FENNECS and steady state simulation results have been compared with Monte Carlo reference solutions using Serpent [15] in combination with the JEFF-3.1.1 continuous energy library. Serpent has also been applied to generate macroscopic cross section libraries in a 12 energy groups structure. With deviations of 86 pcm and 207 pcm for the ARO and ARI control drum states, respectively, satisfactory agreement between FENNECS and Serpent has been obtained.

3.2. High-Resolution Coupled Simulation of Liquid Metal Cooled Minicores at Pin Cell/Subchannel Scale

Important safety-relevant parameters are local variables, e.g., maximum fuel and cladding temperature, i.e., they need to be determined at pin level, not at assembly level. This requires a precise knowledge of the pin-wise distributions of power density and the thermal hydraulic parameters at a subchannel level under stationary and transient conditions. This in turn necessitates the application of coupled codes that simulate the neutronic behavior at pin cell level and the thermal hydraulics at subchannel scale. While so-called pin-by-pin and subchannel multi-physics simulation approaches are already established for Light Water-cooled Reactors (LWR) by, e.g., the Monte Carlo-based coupled code Serpent/SUBCHANFLOW [16] or – at GRS – the deterministic neutron transport-based coupled code TORT TD/CTF [17; 18], such kind of simulation methods is not widely used for the high-fidelity safety assessment of SFRs. Instead, nodal codes like DYN3D [19–21] or PARCS [8] coupled to thermal hydraulic system codes like ATHLET are applied to predict local safety parameters. However, the geometry modeling of nodal codes by regular hexagonal lattices prevents the appropriate discretization of the pin cells of an SFR subassembly and the coolant gap between adjacent subassemblies. FENNECS provides the required geometric flexibility to model clusters of SFR subassemblies with pin cell-wise resolution as is shown in the following at the example of the China Experimental Fast Reactor (CEFR).

Figure 3 shows on the left the ATHLET model of the CEFR fuel assembly with 3 different subchannel types, superimposed on the rod array [22]. The 3 subchannel types also represent the 3 different pin cell types which are used as homogenization areas to generate pin cell homogenized macroscopic cross sections for each pin cell type in 10 energy groups using Serpent and the ENDF/BVII.0 nuclear data library. To account for thermal hydraulic feedback, they are parameterized with respect to fuel temperature, cladding temperature, coolant density and pin lattice pitch, with the latter being used to simulate radial thermal expansion effects.

Figure 3. Left: ATHLET channel representation of a single CEFR fuel assembly with inner (blue), edge (red) and corner (green) channels. Right: Minicore model in FENNECS.

Using the parameterized cross section libraries, a minicore model consisting of 7 fuel assemblies as shown in Figure 3 on the right has been created with FENNECS. The validity of this model has been systematically checked by comparing pin power distributions with a Monte Carlo reference solution obtained with Serpent [22]. The ATHLET model has also been extended to model this minicore. A 1 by 1 feedback mapping is applied between FENNECS and ATHLET, i.e., each pin cell is assigned to an individual thermal hydraulic channel. Convergence between FENNECS and ATHLET is obtained after 8 iterations. The resulting steady state coolant density and fuel temperature distributions are shown in Figure 4 and are physically plausible. However, it should be noted that ATHLET – being a 1-d system code – has the limitation that any Heat Conduction Object (HCO) can be coupled to only one Thermal Fluid Object (TFO). Using the coupled code FENNECS/CTF, when CTF will be available for sodium, will help overcome this limitation.

Figure 4. Steady state coolant density at fuel element outlet (left) and fuel temperature at the core axial midplane (right) [22].

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This paper gives an overview of the current development level of the FEM-based neutron kinetics code FENNECS and its various ranges of application. Though not having been the original motivation for

the development of FENNECS, its applicability to LWR was not only demonstrated but improved by the introduction of the discontinuous Galerkin approach with discontinuity factors. Other major features of FENNECS include (a) the SP3 simplified transport method for both steady state and time dependent simulations, (b) the capability of FENNECS to simulate rotating control drums specific for MMRs and (c) the implementation a projection-based method to minimize the control rod cusping effect for both control drums and conventional control rods. FENNECS along with its geometry meshing tool PEMTY is a module of the GRS code package AC² and can be obtained free of charge from GRS under conditions of Software License Agreement. Future efforts focus on increasing verification and validation and as well implementation of extensions, e.g., to simulate fluid fuel reactor concepts.

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